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REACHING INCLUSIVITY BY RE-DESIGNING EXISTING FACILITIES FOR THE HANDICAPPED ; WITH THE CASE OF TEXTURED PAVING BLOCKS

Hyejung Park / Kwonyong Kang
FEIT, South Korea / Hae An Architecture, South Korea
hyejunghennypark@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to raise awareness to the importance of inclusive way finding methods in public spaces. I propose an inclusive solution using textured paving blocks at the site of COEX mall the largest entertainment mall in Seoul, South Korea.

To begin, I have researched the accessibility, availability and affordability of the COEX mall in order to assess its inclusivity. I then surveyed the current way finding conditions of this site. From these studies I found that COEX mall lacking in its facilities for visually impaired visitors. Textured paving blocks are needed as they hold the potential to be an inclusive indoor way finding. The blocks orientation in space, size, spacing, color and pattern have been carefully considered to be safe, informative, and comprehensive for all types of users: the visually impaired, wheelchair users and able-bodied people.

Keywords: Inclusivity, Wayfinding, Varying users

INTRODUCTION

In public spaces, various users such as children, tourists, foreigners, and able and disable-bodied people share way finding as one of their universal requirements, allowing them to locate main exits, parking lots, restrooms, and information kiosks. In other words, way finding tools need inclusive design, which aims to embrace and accommodate the cultural, and physical differences amongst people. The British Standards Institute (2005) defines inclusive design as "The design of mainstream products and/or services that are accessible to, and usable by, as many people as reasonably possible ...

without the need for special adaptation or specialized design." Julia Casim from the Helen Hamlyn Center (Royal college of Arts) in London says that by understanding the extreme, people can innovate for the mainstream. In this regard, many designers try to universalize everyday products for able-bodied users to reach inclusivity. However, I have found potential within an existing facility for the visually impaired; by making textured paving blocks available to, and usable by non-visually impaired users by reassessing their design.

The objectives of this study are

- To suggest the potential of texture paving blocks as a universal way finding method for non-visually impaired
- To provide recommendations relating to color, size, pattern, and placement of textured paving blocks for the use of varied targets.

USER GROUP

In order to identify specific needs, this research targets the visually impaired, wheelchair users and non-disabled people.

SITE_COEX MALL

COEX Mall is a large shopping arcade located beneath Samsung-dong Trade Center in Gangnam-gu. The mall offers shopping, culture, and entertainment, attracting mostly young people in their teens and early twenties. Located nearby, the COEX exhibition halls and international conference rooms provide convenient shopping for business people. The entrance to the mall is connected to Subway Line No.2 of Samsung Station, and the walls are named under the theme of 'as the water flows,' with names in the order of Summit Walk, Forest Walk, Lake Walk, Waterfall Walk, Canyon Walk, Riverside

Walk, Tropics Walk, Ocean Walk, etc. This watercourse leads you to the Lake Food Court, the event hall featuring various music performances and plays, the large bookstore Bandi & Luni's, the Valley Six fashion mall housing trendy shops selling clothes and accessories, and the Megabox Cineplex with 16 theaters. Also, Korea's largest aquarium is located inside COEX Mall.

Figure 1. Trade Center, COEX mall, Convention Center and Hotel

Accessibility

Since Coex mall is a Mecca for entertainment in Seoul 14 million of people visit per day and 25 million people do so during the weekends. Diverse transportation such as buses, subways and cars are available for convenience visits to the conference center, exhibition halls, hotel, and express bus terminal to International airports. Therefore, facilities for the handicapped at these sites of public transportations are well utilized.

Availability

Coex mall is built underground therefore it becomes a huge weather free zone with 650x290m² area. Even if Coex mall is accessible by public transportation, there are problems in its availability mainly for the visually impaired.

- Absence of textured paving systems
- Lack of Entertaining facilities for people with visual impairment

Affordability

Almost all facilities at Coex mall are on the same floor with the exception of the cinemas and aquarium, so it accommodates people with strollers, children, or disabilities.

However, there are issues with their flow diagram that is derived from streamline forms of water. It is so complicated that people become confused and lost on their way.

COEX	Visually Impaired	Wheelchair User	Able-bodied
Accessibility	☺	☺	☺☺
Availability	☹☹	☺	☺☺
Affordability	☹☹☹	☹☹	☹

Table 1. Inclusive level of COEX mall

WAY FINDING

From aforementioned study, affordability of Coex mall is found generally lower than its accessibility and availability, and it is comparatively lower for the visually impaired than for other users. Despite the complicated structure of pathways, COEX mall offers limited way finding information. There are four interactive map stations and signs, which hang from the ceiling at intersections, but they are hard to find and read. Colors referencing water flow on the floors illustrate only the themes of each space not the pathways (Figure 2 and 3). By refining a method of way finding, affordability of COEX mall can be improved. To be an inclusive way finding method, it needs to be available to many diverse users. Visually impaired people mostly rely on tactile and audio information, while wheelchair users and able-bodied people take visual information because it is more effective, yet tend to avoid tactile information since it becomes a barrier for their mobility. One of the most common tactile way finding methods is the textured paving block system, as it meets the requirements for the visually impaired and also delivers visual information through geometric imagery.

Figure 2. Interactive map stands in front of movie theater.

Figure 3. Signs hung from the ceiling in a space (right above).

TEXTURED PAVING BLOCKS

Textured paving blocks are a tactile language and a navigational cue for pedestrians who are visually impaired. These paving blocks accurately inform visually impaired pedestrians leading the way to main exits, restrooms, elevators and information kiosks. Textured paving blocks are intended primarily for pedestrians with visual impairments, however I found its potential to be tactile as well as visual, as it serves as a map within a space for all pedestrian types. Up until now, the visually impaired walk upon the texture with a long cane and their feet, wheelchair users are forced to navigate the texture, and able-bodied people visually follow the path of the blocks. To redefine the relationship between textured paving blocks and varying users, these different user requirements must be addressed before revisiting its design.

- The bumps on the blocks deflect the front wheels of wheelchairs, making it difficult to move

forward (Tokuda, 2001) or cause the user to tip over. (Figure 4)

- Existing streamlines of textured paving blocks do not inform destinations, but rather direction. When people are in the middle of a space, attempting to navigate towards a main exit, they know that the textured paving blocks connect the main exit to somewhere else, but they get confused as to which direction to take to get to the main exit. (Figure 5)
- When textured paving blocks are laid, it needs to prevent collisions among users in a space.

Considering these issues, this study visits position of textured paving block at the site of COEX mall, regarding its overall size and spacing, color, and pattern.

Figure 4. Truncated bumps deflect the front wheels of a wheelchair as the user try to cross over textured paving blocks and cause the user to tip over or make hard to move forward

Figure 5. Textured paving blocks show only ways not the directions to each facility.

Position

In Figure 6, people walk on the right side of the columns at the mall since they have been culturally educated to take a right side of the aisle to suit the traffic in a space. More horizontal and vertical movement can be found closer to shop entrances as people come and go from the stores. There are benches between each column for a break. Accordingly, space by the columns (Green area on Figure 6) is less crowded and is better suited for installing textured paving blocks for pedestrians with visual impairments. This position makes the textured paving blocks visually available to pedestrians from both sides of the columns. The length of 1.2m shown in Figure 7 is providing distance for personal space from a diagram of Edward T. Hall’s personal reaction bubbles (1990). Visually impaired pedestrians walk on the textured paving blocks by the column, wheelchair users who have low eye level move beside the blocks, and able-bodied pedestrians move between wheelchair users and storefronts as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. A scene of main aisle at COEX mall.

Size and Spacing

The size of one unit of textured paving blocks is primarily 30 by 30 cm with 3 cm diameter bumps. In our experience with a wheelchair user, the bumps on the blocks cause deflection of front wheels of wheelchairs and require interval adjustment among them. In order to allow wheelchairs to cross over the blocks, the size of a textured paving blocks need to correspond to the distance between front wheels of a wheelchair. The average distance between front wheels is 35cm and the maximum thickness of front wheels is 4cm. Since front wheels rotate 360 degree to steer a wheelchair, they need 1cm of extra width on both sides of the wheels in consideration for their vibration. In other words, the distance from the first column to the last column is 33cm is one unit, and the distance from the last column to the next first column is 6cm (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Re-designed textured paving blocks available for wheelchair users to cross over without front wheels caught in intervals.

Figure 7. Position of each pedestrian type between column and storefront: the visually impaired, wheelchair user and the able-bodied.

Color and Pattern

In order to make textured paving blocks work as a visual map, we decided

- To use colors to convey information
- To use patterns to indicate direction.

Safe yellow has been used universally for textured paving blocks and traffic warning signs since it has been found to be highly visually detectable in daylight or brightly-lit situations and in dim light or semi-darkness, even though visual detection depends on the color of the sidewalk as well as the color of the detectable warning (James Jenness & Jeremiah Singer, 2006). If you look at the traffic signs, there are three additional colors; black, red and white on safe yellow backgrounds. Counting on worldwide traffic warning signs that require high readability for people in any condition, those three colors stand out on safe yellow. We also researched disabilities in relation to color discrimination. In a book titled ‘Inclusive design toolkit’ by John Clarkson, Roger Coleman, Ian Hosking and Sam Waller (2007) it states that the most common form of color blindness is red-green color blindness, where the ability to distinguish between colors from red to green in the color spectrum is reduced. The diagram below shows various foreground and background color combinations (Figure 9) and the corresponding simulated appearance for a red-green colorblind person (Figure 10). From comparing these two diagrams, it is found that images with similar brightness contrasts can disappear when viewed by someone with color blindness. Also, we can assume that black and red are more distinguishable by their high contrast to bright backgrounds. White is seen as its own color to a colorblind person. Therefore, black, red and white are chosen for color-coding on textured paving blocks in this study. Black and yellow combination is the most effective contrast, red and yellow combination is the next effective, and white and yellow combination follows later. Therefore, black is the color corresponding with the main exit and subway, which are the most critical facilities for all types of users, especially during emergencies. Red represents a parking space since white has a cultural connotation of hygiene and refers to a restrooms. However, a high contrast of a black and yellow combination has the potential to

spoil the whole atmosphere in a space. While dark grey is less aesthetically imposing than pure black, yet still contrasts yellow, dark grey is used for the color code of textured paving blocks. White is seen as its pure contrast color, but its brightness is close to yellow and can be unclear when used together. To solve this problem, the introduction of a metal frame around each bump is necessary to create contrast

Figure 9. Color combinations (John Clarkson, Roger Coleman, Ian Hosking and Sam Waller, 2007).

Figure 10. The same images viewed with a simulated red-green color blindness (John Clarkson, Roger Coleman, Ian Hosking and Sam Waller, 2007).

Figure 11. Framing each streamline bump and Converting re-designed textured paving blocks in grey scale to check conspicuity of chosen colors; dark grey, red and white on safe yellow.

Figure 12. Comparing ‘Type A: half size of color pattern’ and ‘Type B: two third size of color pattern’.

and avoid the sizzle effect (Figure 11).

Colors on textured paving blocks inform you of destinations and pattern informs you direction. By adjusting proportion of colors on streamline bumps, textured paving blocks become visually directional. We conducted a user test with two different types of color pattern on textured paving blocks shown below; type A and type B and found that type B was

read more comprehensively and directionally with a hint more continuity than type A (Figure 12).

CONCLUSION

Difficulties in daily lives do not come from disabilities, but lack of inclusive consideration to designed products and surroundings. When you designing products that require inclusively, it is not

Figure 13. A map of installation of re-designed textured paving blocks at COEX mall. The blocks connect main exits, subway, parking space, and restrooms.

Figure 14. Illustration of re-designed textured paving blocks installation. Dark grey indicates main exit and subway, red indicates parking space, and white represents restrooms. This figure shows hot wheelchair users cross over the blocks.

necessary to begin from nothing to create innovation. By re-considering the details of existing products and facilities, we can reach inclusive innovation in design. This research remains incomplete and requires a number of user tests to confirm improved usability by users such as the disabled, the elderly, and children. Also, there are numerous opportunities to utilize GPS navigation and audio alert systems in combination with the paving blocks to help guide diverse populations through spaces and to the exits in the event of emergencies.

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